

IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center Target Enablement Resource

INPP5D (SHIP1) Bioinformatics

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Authors	Jie Zhang, Kun Huang
Collaborating Authors	Jun Wan, Travis Johnson, Shunian Xiang
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Affiliations	Indiana University School of Medicine

Introduction

As the bioinformatic core of TREAT-AD target prioritization, we have performed a series of analyses on drug target INPP5D/SHIP1. These analyses include both data driven hypothesis generation using genome-wide transcriptomic and epigenomic data as well as targeted study on INPP5D based on pathway analysis and differential expression analysis. The hypothesis generation process is also an interactive process with input from other cores in the IUSM-Purdue TREAT-AD Center based on various selection criteria which will be discussed in the later sections of this report. In addition, there are additional target candidates going through a similar selection process.

Frequent gene co-expression network mining identified microglia specific gene modules in AD

Gene co-expression network analysis is a powerful bioinformatics tool to identify genes that are involved in common biological processes, regulatory networks, and cell-specific expression. Given the large amount of publicly available gene expression datasets for AD, an important question is: are there any genes that show strong co-expression relationships in AD and human brains? By identifying genes that are co-expressed in AD, we can identify potential AD specific processes and cell types. To ensure the robustness of the analysis, we have established a mature pipeline and co-expression network mining algorithm for identifying frequently co-expressed gene modules using multiple datasets [1-3]. We have previously mined frequently co-expressed gene modules for AD using 3-5 datasets [4, 5] and identified multiple co-

expressed gene modules in AD. Here we further expanded the frequent network mining using eight large datasets as listed in Table 1.

Table 1 | AD and normal brain transcriptomic datasets.

Dataset	AD samples	Normal samples	Brain region
GSE5281	87	74	Middle Temporal Gyrus (MTG), Posterior Cingulate Cortex (PCC), Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Hippocampus (HC), Superior Frontal Cortex (SFG), Primary Visual Cortex (VCX)
GSE48350	80	173	Entorhinal Cortex (EC), Post-central Gyrus (PCG2), Superior Frontal Gyrus (SFG), Hippocampus (HC)
GSE33000	310	157	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex(DLPFC)
GSE44772	387	129	Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex (DLPFC), Visual Cortex (VC)
ROSMAP	224	201	Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC)
MSBB	409	273	Frontal pole (BM10), Superior temporal gyrus (BM22), Parahippocampal gyrus (BM36), Inferior frontal gyrus (BM44)
Mayo	82	78	Temporal cortex (TC)
ABA	30	56	Hippocampus(HC), Temporal Cortex (TCx), Parietal Cortex(PC), Forebrain White Matter(FWM)

By applying the algorithm and process developed in [4], we identified multiple frequently co-expressed gene modules. Table 2 shows two gene modules most significantly enriched in microglia related biological processes.

Table 2. Gene modules that are strongly enriched with microglia genes. Red genes are potential candidate genes proposed by the center. The left module is identified using AD brain samples and the right module is from normal brain samples.

AD3_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74	N5_8Data_freq_0.05_unnormalized_0.74
ABI3, ARHGAP30, ARHGDIB, ARPC1B, BTK, C1QA, C1QB, C3, C3AR1, CD300A, CD74, CD86, CSF1R , CSF3R, CTSS, CYBA, CYBB, CYTL1, DOCK2, DOCK8, FCGR2A, FLI1, FPR1, GIMAP4, GIMAP6, GIMAP8, GPSM3, HAVCR2, HCK, HCLS1, HLA-DMB, HLA-DOA, HLA-DRA, IFI30, IL10RA, INPP5D , ITGAM, ITGB2, LAIR1, LCP1, LGALS9, LILRA2, LY86, MFNG, MS4A4A, MS4A6A, MS4A7, MYO1F, NCKAP1L, PIK3AP1, PLCG2 , PLEK, PTPN6, PTPRC, RHBDF2, RNASE6, SERPINA1, SIPA1, SLA, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, SLC7A7, SLCO2B1, STK10, SYK, TAL1, TBXAS1, TLR2, TLR7, TMEM119, TREM2, TYROBP , VAV1, VSIG4, WAS, WDFY4	PLEK, LAT2, BTK, ITGB2, STEAP3, LCP1, CD86, PTPRC, PYGL, HLA-DMB, HCLS1, CD14, LY86, C3, CYBA, TYROBP, PIK3AP1, HLA-DRA, AIF1, BLNK, SYK, SLC1A5, SLC2A5, CYBB, NCKAP1L, DOCK8, HCK, TREM2, C1QA, SLA, ITGAM, FCGR2A, SCIN, WDFY4, IFI30, SERPINA1, MS4A6A, STAB1, FCGR1A, PARP9, LAIR1, DOCK2, CD300A, C1QB, FPR1, ALPK1, CASP1, CCR1, TBXAS1

While both gene modules are enriched in microglia functions, the AD module is much larger with important genes such as INPP5D and PLCG2. Both gene modules contain well-known AD genes such as TREM2. Pathway analysis using Ingenuity Pathway Analysis (IPA) also confirmed the AD gene module is highly enriched in immune function genes, as shown in the figure on the right.

INPP5D is specifically expressed in AD brains

An ideal target will be genes with low expression levels in normal brain tissues while high in AD brains. We first checked the gene expression levels for a selected group of genes of interest. As shown in the figure below, among all tissues, INPP5D is highly expressed in EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood and small intestine. INPP5D has very low expression levels in normal brain tissues. Furthermore, the brain regions with relatively higher INPP5D are not focal areas of AD (i.e., substantia nigra, hypothalamus).

Genes	Brain expression in general	Highest expression in brain	High expression in tissues
INPP5D	Low (5-20)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, hypothalamus	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
PLCG2	Extremely low (2-4)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra, basal ganglia	EBV-transformed lymphocytes, spleen, whole blood, small intestine
CSF1R	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, substantia nigra	spleen
STAT3	Medium (<50)	Spinal cord, cerebellar hemisphere	All other tissues except brain
ABCA7	Medium (<50)	cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Whole blood, pituitary, spleen
PTK2B	High (>100)	cerebellar hemisphere, cerebellum	Brain, EBV-transformed lymphocytes, whole blood

We further compared gene expression levels of INPP5D between AD and normal tissues in five datasets and results are summarized in Table 3. In all five datasets, INPP5D is significantly overexpressed in AD brain samples with fold-change ranges from 1.2 to 1.5.

Table 3. Differential gene expression analysis for INPP5D

Dataset	log2 FC AD vs. Normal	Ave Expression levels	t-stat	P.Value	adj.P.Val
GSE48350	0.387745841	8.134132818	6.042989852	5.35E-09	1.19E-07
GSE5281	0.628882854	4.433585413	7.383595196	7.12E-12	1.69E-10
MSBB	0.498083953	4.101808234	8.924332217	4.05E-18	8.58E-16
ROSMAP	0.26063898	2.57548141	4.72332342	3.15E-06	0.00018639
GSE33000	0.577774108	1.165034887	13.84229345	9.43E-37	1.15E-35

INPP5D functions as a hub gene in immune response networks

We searched IPA for potential regulation, interactions, and pathway intersections between INPP5D/SHIP1 and the rest of the Year1 target candidates including PLCG2 (See figure below). IPA analysis identified that INPP5D/SHIP1 functions as a hub to link PLCG2, TYROBP, IL10 and several other immune response genes/proteins.

For the IPA canonical pathways involving INPP5D and PLCG2 by IPA, analysis showed the two are involved in multiple immune response pathways and phagosome formation. The x-axis of the figure is in the -log10 scale and thus the larger the number, the smaller the p-value for the enrichment analysis.

Canonical Pathways from IPA

Using TopGene tool, we also identified key pathways in which the selected genes are highly enriched as shown below which include interleukin signaling pathway, cytokine signaling pathway and functions in the adaptive immune system.

Targets involved pathways

Pathway	Source	No. Mol.	Total	Involved targets
IL-10 Anti-inflammatory Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	4	17	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Interleukin signaling pathway	PantherDB	5	92	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
IL22 Soluble Receptor Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	16	IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signaling by Interleukins	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	531	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Epstein-Barr virus infection	BioSystems: KEGG	5	203	SPI1,IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,PLCG2
PDGF signaling pathway	PantherDB	4	127	PDGFA,STAT3,STAT4,PLCG2
Cytokine Signaling in Immune system	BioSystems: REACTOME	7	763	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3
Osteoclast differentiation	BioSystems: KEGG	4	130	SPI1,TREM2,TYROBP,PLCG2
Bioactive Peptide Induced Signaling Pathway	MSigDB C2 BIOCARTA (v6.0)	3	43	PTK2B,STAT3,STAT4
Jak-STAT signaling pathway	BioSystems: KEGG	4	156	IL10,IL10RA,STAT3,STAT4
Signal regulatory protein (SIRP) family interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	13	PTK2B,TYROBP
EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance	BioSystems: KEGG	3	79	PDGFA,STAT3,PLCG2
JAK/STAT signaling pathway	PantherDB	2	16	STAT3,STAT4
Other semaphorin interactions	BioSystems: REACTOME	2	19	TREM2,TYROBP
Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	BioSystems: KEGG	4	270	IL10,PDGFA,IL10RA,IL1RAP
Adaptive Immune System	BioSystems: REACTOME	6	826	TREM2,PDGFA,TYROBP,CD33,INPP5D,PLCG2

INPP5D interacts with key immune response genes and kinases

In addition, we searched the STRING protein-protein interaction database for INPP5D focusing on proteins/genes with immediate interactions. As shown in the figure, INPP5D is a hub of the PPI network in the STRING database, tightly interacting with TIGIT, KLRG1, GRB2, PIK3R1, ITPKB, FCGR2B, PTPN6, SHC1, PTPN11, BTK, many of them are involved in immune response or protein kinase/phosphatase activity.

The interacting proteins/genes are listed below with their functions and type of interactions.

Your Input:

INPP5D
 Phosphatidylinositol 3,4,5-trisphosphate 5-phosphatase 1; Phosphatidylinositol (PtdIns) phosphatase that specifically hydrolyzes the 5-phosphate of phosphatidylinositol-3,4,5-trisphosphate (PtdIns(3,4,5)P₃) to produce PtdIns(3,4)P₂, thereby negatively regulating the PI3K (phosphoinositide 3-kinase) pathways. Acts as a negative regulator of B-cell antigen receptor signaling. Mediates signaling from the FC-gamma-R1IB receptor (FCGR2B), playing a central role in terminating signal transduction from activating immune/hematopoietic cell receptor systems. Acts as a negative regulator of mye [...] (1189 aa)

Predicted Functional Partners:

		Neighborhood	Gene Fusion	Cooccurrence	Coexpression	Experiments	Databases	Textmining	Homology/	Score
SHC1	SHC-transforming protein 1; Signaling adapter that couples activated growth factor receptors to signaling pathways. Participat...			●	●	●	●	●		0.999
FCGR2B	Low affinity immunoglobulin gamma Fc region receptor II-b; Receptor for the Fc region of complexed or aggregated immunogl...			●	●	●	●	●		0.998
GRB2	Growth factor receptor-bound protein 2; Adapter protein that provides a critical link between cell surface growth factor recepto...			●	●	●	●	●		0.991
DOK1	Docking protein 1; DOK proteins are enzymatically inert adaptor or scaffolding proteins. They provide a docking platform for th...			●	●	●	●	●		0.986
KLRG1	Killer cell lectin-like receptor subfamily G member 1; Plays an inhibitory role on natural killer (NK) cells and T-cell functions upo...						●	●		0.966
TIGIT	T-cell immunoreceptor with Ig and ITIM domains; Binds with high affinity to the poliovirus receptor (PVR) which causes increas...							●		0.963
ITPKB	Inositol-trisphosphate 3-kinase B							●		0.962
PIK3R1	Phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase regulatory subunit alpha; Binds to activated (phosphorylated) protein-Tyr kinases, through its SH...						●	●		0.962
BTK	Tyrosine-protein kinase BTK; Non-receptor tyrosine kinase indispensable for B lymphocyte development, differentiation and sig...						●	●		0.962
PTPN11	Tyrosine-protein phosphatase non-receptor type 11; Acts downstream of various receptor and cytoplasmic protein tyrosine kin...						●	●		0.960

TopGene analysis also revealed multiple interactions with pathways of JAK1, CSF1R, SYK, PTPN11, PIK3R1.

Interaction	No. Mol.	Total Mol.	Involved targets
JAK1 interactions	5	129	IL10RA,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
CSF1R interactions	4	47	SPI1,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
SYK interactions	5	141	PTK2B,TYROBP,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
TYROBP interactions	3	19	TREM2,TYROBP,INPP5D
PTPN11 interactions	5	253	PTK2B,CD33,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
PIK3R1 interactions	5	319	IL1RAP,PTK2B,INPP5D,STAT3,PLCG2
IL10RA interactions	2	5	IL10,IL10RA

INPP5D/SHIP1 interaction with the inflammasome (Pycard, NALP1, caspase-1, caspase-5)

IPA analysis revealed INPP5D is indirectly linked to inflammasome members through multiple types of Ig proteins. Please see figure below.

IPA network showing possible interactions between inflammasome with our drug targets

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